

Steam turbine controllers design based on soft-computing techniques

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Jul 20, 2020

Revised Aug 5, 2020

Accepted Sep 9, 2020

Keywords:

ACOA

FLC

GA

IMC-PID controller

Steam turbine

ABSTRACT

Steam turbine is viewed as a standout among hotspots for control age in the most recent decades, its elements examination ends up being dynamically more basic. For this investigation, the model chose is of turbine speed control framework. The purpose behind this is that model is regularly experienced in refineries in a type of steam turbine that utilization hydraulic governor to control the speed of the turbine. To suit plan prerequisites, a mathematical model for the turbine was determined in light of transfer function and state space definition. There are two sorts of controllers for steam turbines which are traditional and modern controllers. Internal mode control with proportional integral derivative (IMC-PID) and linear quadratic controller (LQR) are classical type. Fuzzy logic controller (FLC) and intelligent optimization techniques like, ant colony algorithm (ACOA) and genetic algorithm (GA) are modern type. The proposed work centers on classical verses modern controllers. Results got demonstrate that embracing such a controller (GA) improves the design requirements and transient stability. The system control was actualized in simulation utilizing MATLAB/Simulink.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Over the span of late 100 years, the steam turbines have been comprehensively used to control making due to their efficiencies and costs. With respect to point of confinement, application and needed execution, a substitute level of versatile quality is offered for the structure of steam turbines [1]. The steam turbine is a stream machine, which changes warm vitality into mechanical vitality, there are numerous papers for displaying the turbine, such as utilizing neural systems, the utilization of neural systems, genetic algorithms (GAs), fuzzy frameworks or a blend of these hypotheses for the demonstrating of modern procedures, for example, power plants have been utilized generally in ongoing years [2-4]. In general, steam turbines are complex machines in which an extensive variety of multidisciplinary components associate. A turbine with various segments may be either pair compound or cross-compound. In a couple compound turbine, the regions are all on one shaft, with a lone generator, strangely, a cross-compound turbine contain two shafts, each related with a generator and driven by no less than one turbine segment. Another approach in numerical displaying of thermodynamic cycles and electric intensity of utility region warming and co-generation steam turbines. The approach depends on the use of the dimensionless mass streams, which portray the thermodynamic cycle of a combined heat and power steam turbine [5, 6]. Steam temperature must be steady to accomplish top turbine effectiveness and lessen exhaustion in the turbine cutting blades. Ordinary proportional-integral-derivative (PID) based control plans require complex gain scheduling and lead-lag feed forward compensation for stack changes and burner tilt [7].

Fuzzy logic controller (FLC) is one of the succeed controller utilized as a part of the procedure control if there should arise an occurrence of model vulnerabilities. There are numerous parameters in fuzzy controller can be adjusted. The Speed control of turbine unit development and activity can be utilized, Adaptive controller is recommended here to adjust standardized fuzzy controller [8, 9]. The best trouble of the control framework combination is streamlining models and strategies outline the steam turbine automatic control framework is connected to stabilize turbine rotor recurrence with high accuracy. The intelligent steam turbine control framework is one technique to utilize GAs to solve numerous issues [10]. There are many papers utilized traditional controller outline, pole placement procedure to control the turbine speed [11] and PID for single-loop control of turbine speed control framework by approximating the closed-loop type of an internal mode controller with disposal of higher-arrange terms in the controller frame to classical (PID) shape for robust operation [12], The adequacy of the proposed control activities are exhibited through some computer simulations, yet every one of these strategies suffers from numerous issues, such as, putting the controller poles (closed-loop poles) at the coveted area and needs calibrating [13, 14]. these are recommended that the controller be tuned utilizing adaptive fuzzy controller, where the adaptive controller is a stochastic worldwide pursuit strategy that imitates the procedure of common advancement, however this needs more experience of the framework and primary prerequisites must be accomplished. The best trouble of the control framework blend is optimization models and techniques design. [15] proposed intelligent control arrangement of steam turbine utilizing GA, it must consider all auxiliary and mechanical necessities created to them. Section 2 presents the development and outlining of turbine construction modeling. Section 3 explains the development and planning of fundamental controllers are portrayed. Section 4 elaborate the outlines discussion and comparison between all controllers. Finally, Section 5 summarizes incorporates conclusion.

2. TURBINE MODELING

In order to portray the transient elements of steam turbines subsections, the numerical models are first created in light of the energy adjust, thermodynamic standards and semi-observational conditions. The hydraulic driven turbine elements affect the dynamic stability of the power framework. This segment gives a review of the displaying of the power frameworks dynamic. In steam turbine the stored energy of high-power steam is changed over into turning energy, which at that point is changed over into electrical energy in the generator [16]. In control framework studies, nonlinearities in the speed-control instrument are ordinarily ignored, so that, Let the steam turbine and their elements are linear models. The control yield from turbine is controlled through the situation of control valves, which control the stream of steam to the turbine. Figure 1 demonstrates the schematic-graph of turbine speed control.

Figure 1. Schematic-diagram of turbine speed control [12]

The explanation behind that is model is frequently experienced in refineries in a type of steam turbine that utilization water powered driven generator to control the speed of the turbine as delineated in Figure 1. The complexities of the generator controller will not be considered in this paper. The electronic representative controller is a noteworthy subject by it and it is past the degree of this examination. In any case this study will center on the model that makes up the steam turbine and water powered generator to control the speed of the turbine. With regards to refineries, you can consider the steam turbine as the core of

the system, because of the route that in the refineries, there are heaps of high points of confinement blowers running on steam turbine. Subsequently the control and the tuning advancement of the steam turbine take long time and critical. The transfer function of the conveying valve and gate servomotor is:

$$G_1(s) = \frac{1}{\tau_1 s} \quad (1)$$

where (τ_1) is time-constant of valve. The transfer function of the pilot valve and pilot servomotor is:

$$G_2(s) = \frac{1}{(1 + \tau_2 s)} \quad (2)$$

where (τ_2) is time-constant of sensor. Finally, the transfer function of compressor is:

$$G_3(s) = \frac{1}{(1 + \tau_3 s)} \quad (3)$$

where (τ_3) is the time-constant of the compressor. The overall transfer function [12] and [14] is:

$$G_p(s) = \frac{1}{\tau_1 s (1 + \tau_2 s) (1 + \tau_3 s)} \quad (4)$$

After substituting the values of time-constants, the overall transfer function is [14]:

$$G_p(s) = \frac{1}{s(s + 1)(s + 5)} \quad (5)$$

Figure 2 demonstrates the transient reaction of the framework, where greatest overshoot $Mp = 0\%$, but sluggish reaction, the settling time $Ts = 15$ sec, and rise time $Tr = 8.33$ sec. For a good following of input signal, a second order all around damped framework has been chosen as [17]:

$$\frac{C(s)}{R(s)} = \frac{Wn^2}{(s^2 + 2\zeta Wn + Wn^2)} \quad (6)$$

Damping specified by ($\zeta = 0.9$) and speed of response defined by natural frequency coefficient ($Wn = 3 \text{ rad/sec}$). These design requirements give ($Mp \leq 0.63\%$) and ($Ts \leq 1.4$ sec), while the rise time ($Tr \leq 0.889$ sec).

Figure 2. Transient response of the system

3. CONTROLLERS DESIGN

There are numerous controllers for steam turbine can be grouped amongst traditional and present day (clever) controllers. In this paper, taking internal mode with proportional derivative and integral controller (IMC-PID), linear quadratic regulator (LQR), FLC, and finally contrasts all these with intelligent algorithms, like ant colony algorithm (ACOA) and GA controllers.

3.1. IMC-PID controller

The PID controller is well known controllers in industry. As a result of its straightforward structure and great vigor in an extensive variety of working conditions, it is utilized as a part of an assortment of modern procedures, for example, metallurgy and synthetic procedures [18]. Morari and his associates [19] have built up a vital new control framework technique that is IMC. The IMC approach has two essential preferences.

- It expressly considers demonstrate uncertainty.
- It enables the designer to trade-off control execution against control framework.

In the IMC definition, the controller is constructing straightforwardly in light of the “great” some portion of the procedure transfer function. The IMC definition for the most part brings about just a single tuning parameter (λ). The PID tuning parameters are then an element of it. The determination of the closed-loop time constant is specifically identified with the robustness (affect ability to system model error) of the closed-loop framework [20]. Here the IMC-PID controller tuning system not just has the benefit of internal model control, yet in addition incorporates the normal for traditional PID controller. The IMC-PID tuning strategies [21–23] and the direct synthesis (DS) method [24] are run of the mill tuning techniques in view of accomplishing a desired closed-loop reaction. The strength is enhanced by including a low pass filter, which weakens the impact of framework demonstrating uncertainty, which more often effects at high frequency and gives great input following. The transfer function of IMC controllers:

$$G_f(s) = \frac{1}{(\lambda s + 1)^n} \quad (7)$$

where (n) is the filter order and choosing it is very important for realizable controller. (λ) is time constant and values of it depends on the speed response.

Ref [12] gives more points of interest for picking (λ), and watch that (λ) influences the proportional gain (K_p) just, while the dynamic framework (time constants) affects the estimation of integral time (T_i) and derivative time (T_d). Picking ($\lambda = 0.1$) and $n = 2$. We can computed $K_p = 1$, and $K_d = 1.2$, on the grounds that the framework model (5) is type one, so on need to integral action, where the steady-state error equal zero. Figure 3 demonstrates the transient reaction with IMC-PID controller, where ($T_s = 7.96sec$), ($T_r = 4.72sec$) and ($M_p = 0\%$). This technique needs all the more tuning for (λ) to satisfy the design requirements.

Figure 3. Transient response with IMC-PID controller

3.2. LQR controller

The goal in LQR configuration is to choose a state-variable feedback (SVFB) control (K) that limits the execution index (J). The plan method for calculating the LQR (K) is appeared in Figure 4. The design procedures are [25]:

- Select plan parameter frameworks Q and R.
- Solve the algebraic Riccati equation for P.
- Find the SVFB using $K = R^{-1}B^T P$

Firstly, the system model (5) must convert to: $\dot{x} = Ax + Bu$, where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -5 & -6 \end{bmatrix} \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad C = [1 \ 0 \ 0] \quad D = 0 \quad (8)$$

where C and D are not utilized as a part of SVFB outline. In outlining LQR controller, for steam turbine speed, it must decide the estimation of (K) which decided the feedback control law. This is finished by picking two parameter esteems, input $R = 0.1$ and $Q = C' * C$. After applying MATLAB statement: $[K, S, E] = lqr(A, B, Q, R)$. The feedback gains are $K = [3.1623 \ 3.1311 \ 0.5009]$. Figure 5 shows the transient response with LQR controller where, $(Ts = 6.73sec)$ and $(Tr = 3.91sec)$, so that the design requirements are not meet. It is clear vital to understand that this advanced control approach to manage criticism design way is different from the logic of classical control. It is described by:

- Chose Q and R that are fixing to the close loop performance (needs all the more tuning)
- Introducing an intermediate amount P
- Solving a Riccati equation.
- Calculating an ensured arrangement for stabilizes the framework.
- Computing nearly knowledge into the strength or structure of the system.
- Also require a prefilter (N) to make steady-state error with zero, in this outline the estimation of pre-filter is (3.162).

Figure 4. Block-diagram of LQR controller

Figure 5. Transient response with LQR controller

3.3. Intelligent controllers

It is a class of control strategies that utilization different processing approaches, as neural system, fuzzy logic, and GAs. This paper centers around ideal tuning of PID controller for the steam turbine framework using FLC, ACOA, GA for the purpose to comparing between them and classical controllers IMC-PID and LQR.

3.3.1. FLC

The field of fuzzy control has been gaining quick ground as of late. FLC has been broadly misused for nonlinear, high order and time delay framework [26]. For steam turbine framework an FLC can be done with basic approach and smaller number of rules (four rules) as it gives an indistinguishable execution from by the larger run set [27–29].

For this study, just two fuzzy membership functions are utilized for the two input error sources (e) and derivative of error ($\dot{e}$) as appeared in Figure 6. The fuzzy participation functions for the output parameter are appeared in Figure 7. Here, N means negative, Z means zero, and P mean positive. The fuzzy linguistic principles are characterized from the desired reaction of the system (for damping ratio = 0.9 and natural frequency = 3rad/sec).

Four rules were determined for FLC, see Table 1. These four principles are adequate to cover every single conceivable circumstance [29]. The Simulink model of FLC, it shows in Figure 8, with steam turbine system. Step reaction of the controlled steam turbine are appeared in Figure 9 where $T_s = 6.45 \text{ sec}$ and $T_r = 3.55 \text{ sec}$, here the factors gains (K_p, K_d) in Figure 8 are picked (1,1.2) individually as chosen from Section 3.1 IMC-PID plan method, so that to improve the reaction and fulfilled the outline necessities needs tuning these factors.

Figure 6. Membership functions for the two inputs

Figure 7. Membership functions for the output

Table 1. Fuzzy rules

		$\dot{e}$	
u		N	P
e	N	N	Z
	P	Z	P

Figure 8. Simulink model of FLC with steam turbine system

Figure 9. Shows the transient response with FLC

3.3.2. ACOA

ACO was proposed by [30]. An ACO algorithm is advanced heuristic calculations. Numerous execution plans are performed by ACO calculation to acquire the ideal PID controller parameters of steam turbine framework. For tuning PID Controller, in this method, the target work considered depends on the error minimization [31]. The execution of a controller is best assessed as far as error criterion. Various such criteria are accessible. Presently, issue ought to be composed as an optimization issue and after that be solved. Choosing target work is the most critical piece of this enhancement issue. Since, picking distinctive target capacities may totally change the ant’s variety state.

$$e(t) = Y(t) - R(t) \tag{9}$$

A few structures to limit the error, like integral square error (ISE), integral time absolute error (ITAE), integral absolute error (IAE), yet in this work, it chooses integral of time multiplied square error (ITSE).

$$F = \int_0^t te^2(t) dt \tag{10}$$

With a specific end goal to misuse the ACO calculation, it is smarter to speak to our streamlining issue by an immediate path as development graph, see Figure 10. There are numerous means for the outline refer to [32] for more points of interest. ACO calculation has the accompanying parameters: α and β = constants that decide the relative impact of the pheromone esteems and the heuristic qualities on the choice of the ant, NA=number of ants, σ =the vanishing rate. These estimations of NA, σ , α , β are chosen after many experiments, and these qualities are: NA=100, $\sigma = 0.7$, $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = 2$, and maximum generation=200.

Figure 10. ACO optimization graph [32]

At first, every parameter (K_p , T_i , T_d) is randomly and consistently dispersed with a normal value which is equivalent to the value established by Ziegler-Nichols ($K_p = 18$, $T_i = 1.404$ sec, $T_d = 0.351$ sec) of steam turbine speed. After a few cycles, the multi target ant colony algorithm province calculation, that creates the best arrangements of the PID parameters (K_p , T_i , T_d) of the steam turbine speed framework. All the calculation is actualized with MATLAB/Simulink. Figure 11 demonstrates the transient reaction with ACOA., still needs additionally running and increment the quantity of cycles or increment number of ants, to fulfill the plan requirements.

Figure 11. Transient response with ACOA

3.3.3. GA

The present time the best techniques for multiextremal improvement are (GAs) [33]. The reason for optimization of the control frameworks by (GA) comprises in finding the most ideal choice of enhancement assignment by one or couple of criteria. To optimize a structure utilizing a (GA) it is expected to set some quantify of value for each structure in look space. The function of fitness is utilized for this reason. During maximization, the target work transforms itself into a fitness function. For the assignments of minimization, it is important to transform a target work and displace it after that to the region of positive qualities. Technique of search of ideal arrangement in (GA) depends on the theory of determination.

If to accept that to acknowledge that each person of populace is a point in facilitate space of advancement assignment $X_i [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i]$ and fitness of an individual is the best possible estimation of target work $F(X_i)$ at that point singular populaces can be analyzed as great number of arrange focuses in space, and procedure of development as movement of these focuses toward the change of estimations of target work.

An element of the (GA) as a global inquiry technique is that none of genetic administrators in the relative's age procedure inclines toward information of nearby help reaction surface for the objective function [34]. Framing of relatives by genetic administrators happens in an irregular way, and that is the reason there is no certification that discovered arrangements will be superior to fatherly. The specified highlights control wide use of GA in designing practice. Anyway need in such calculations for the arrangement of the connected undertakings of similarly little measurement always develops, particularly regarding the arranged inclination of presentation of fuzzy and neural network system in the control frameworks.

Generally, in this paper, to implement and design GA, there are ten sub-programs written in MATLAB. They are `arithXover`, `ga`, `Initial_PID_GA`, `initializega`, `initializeoga`, `maxGenTerm`, `normGeomSelect`, `PID_objfun_MSE`, `roulette`, `unifMutation` where in `PID_objfun_MSE` sub-program, insert the system under control (5) and the excitable sub-program is `Initial_PID_GA`. In Figure 12, it appears the block-diagram of GA.

Figure 12. The block-diagram of GA

The procedure of optimization is computed by amplification of the fitness function (F) which is the mean error between the present estimation of the framework yield and the input reference:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{t} \int_0^T (e(t))^2 dt \tag{11}$$

$$fitness = \frac{1}{MSE} \tag{12}$$

In this work GA parameters are taken by the experimentation strategy is expressed as takes after:

- Population size = 80;
- Crossover rate = 0.4;
- Mutation rate = 0.01;
- Maximum generation = 100.

Figure 13 demonstrates the reaction of the framework with utilizing GA.

Figure 13. The transient reaction with GA

4. RESULTS COMPARISON AND DISCUSSION

It is watched that GA gives better execution when contrasted and others, however GA sets aside 55.334568 seconds computational time for tuning the PID controller. The parameters of PID which are gotten

by utilizing GA are: $K_p = 155.7678$, $K_d = 58.1440$. The responses of all controllers are compared with respect to settling time, rise time, maximum overshoot, and steady-state error; and it is tabulated in Table 2. It is clear that LQR is better in speed response compared with IMC-PID, but needs additional hardware (prefilter) to remove the steady state error, while using soft-computing techniques (FLC, ACOA, GA) can improve the design requirements, and the best method is (GA), where the transient response of turbine speed, satisfied the desired input in short rise and settling time.

Table 2. Comparison between all controllers

Controller types	Settling time (sec)	Rise time (sec)	Max. overshoot (%)	Steady-state error
IMC-PID	7.96	4.72	0	0
LQR	6.73	3.91	0	0 (need prefilter)
FLC	6.45	3.55	0	0
ACOA	2.14	1.31	0	0
GA	0.0167	0.0085	0.217	0

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, soft-computing controllers are used. The strength of the system controlled by the AG is compared with the system controlled by the traditional IMC-PID, LQR controllers, also with another intelligent, like FLC and ACOA. As indicated by the recreation brings about MATLAB, demonstrate that GA can enhance the power and little overshoot and quick reaction (less T_s and T_r). For turbine speed control the quicker reaction to look into strength, the better is the outcome for the framework. The established strategy is useful for the beginning stage of what are the PID esteems. Anyway the approached is closer in determining the underlying PID esteems utilizing established technique is somewhat troublesome. There are numerous means and furthermore by experimentation in getting the PID esteems before you can limit in drawing near to the “advanced” qualities. Upgraded calculations were executed in the framework to see and concentrate how the framework reaction is. These were accomplished through actualizing the ACO and GA. Simulation results demonstrate that the ACOA optimization has a better control system performance compared with traditional approach and FLC, but from Table 2, it is found that the rise and settling time has improved by using GA.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to thank Mustansiriyah University (www.uomustansiriyah.edu.iq), Baghdad, Iraq for its support in the present work.

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